

EMP-G 2025 OnSSET TANZANIA ELECTRIFICATION PLAN 2030

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Keywords

AfDB	African Development Bank
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth
ESMAP	Energy Sector Management Assistance Program
EWURA	The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority
GEP	Global Electrification Platform
GIS	Geographic Information System
ICTP	Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics
MoE	Ministry of Energy
MoF	Ministry of Finance
MV	Medium Voltage
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
OnSSET	Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool
PV	Photovoltaic
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
REA	Rural Electrification Agency
SEforAll	Sustainable Energy for All
SHS	Solar Home Systems
TANESCO	Tanzania Electric Supply Company Limited
PSMP 2024	Power System Master Plan Update 2025
VETA	The Vocational Education and Training Authority
WB	World Bank

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Executive Summary

This report presents a comparative analysis of two national electrification scenarios for Tanzania, developed using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) as part of the Energy Modelling Platform – Global 2025 (EMP-G) initiative. The study models least-cost technology pathways to achieve electricity access targets of 75% under the Power System Master Plan (PSMP 2024) and 100% under the Tanzania M300 Energy Compact (2025) by the year 2030.

Key Findings

- Under the PSMP 2024 scenario, 75% of the population is projected to be electrified by 2030, mainly through grid densification (50%) followed by..., while 25% mostly in rural, low-density areas, remains unelectrified.
- The M300 Energy Compact scenario demonstrates that universal access (100%) is technically and economically feasible by 2030. It combines grid densification (49.7%), grid extension (12.5%), with significant contributions from Solar Home Systems (29.5%) and mini grids (8.3%).
- Achieving universal access will require an estimated investment of USD 8.94 billion, compared to USD 5.29 billion for 75% access under business-as-usual conditions.

Recommendations

- Develop a national electrification dashboard for real-time monitoring of access, investment flows, and implementation progress. (MoE, TANESCO, REA, NBS)
- Integrate spatial planning tools such as OnSSET and QGIS into national and regional energy planning frameworks. (MoE, REA, TANESCO)
- Scale up investment in off-grid solutions through climate finance, PPPs, and results-based financing. (MoE, MoF, REA)
- Update regulatory instruments to streamline mini-grid licensing and enhance grid-off-grid interoperability. (EWURA, MoE)
- Strengthen institutional and human capacity for planners and technicians at the national and local levels. (MoE, TANESCO, VETA, SEforALL)

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This study aims to support Tanzania's national electrification agenda by identifying the least-cost pathways to achieve 75% and 100% electricity access by 2030. It leverages the OnSSET tool in alignment with PSMP 2024 and the National Energy Compact 2025.

1.2 Scope

The study models electrification scenarios based on PSMP 2024 and the National Energy Compact 2025, assessing spatial, technical, and economic feasibility. It compares centralized grid, mini-grid, and standalone solutions across rural and urban areas.

1.3 Objectives

The objective is to determine the most cost-effective and technically viable electrification technologies. Through geospatial modeling, the study evaluates access strategies that optimize investment and infrastructure rollout.

1.4 Connection to M300

This work aligns with the M300 Initiative for African countries to connect 300 million people to electricity by 2030. It enhances Tanzania's planning capacity and supports donor coordination by providing actionable insights to accelerate universal energy access.

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach

This study employed the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) to assess least-cost electrification strategies across Tanzania. OnSSET performs spatially explicit, settlement level analyses to determine the most economical electrification option (Grid densification and extension, mini-grids, or standalone systems). The modelling was executed using Python in Jupyter Notebook within an Anaconda environment, with spatial preprocessing and visualization done in QGIS.

Two scenarios were developed based on national policy priorities: the Power System Master Plan 2024 (PSMP 2024) and the Tanzania Energy Compact 2025. Key inputs included geospatial population distribution, grid infrastructure, renewable energy resources, and transport accessibility. Data sources included WorldPop, the 2022 Census, TANESCO and REA GIS data, ESMAP's Global Solar Atlas, Global Wind Atlas, and OpenStreetMap. All datasets were harmonized in QGIS and prepared in CSV format compatible with OnSSET.

2.2 Assumptions

The model used consistent demographic and technical parameters across both scenarios. These included:

Parameters	Values
Base year	2024
Target year	2030
Population 2024	67,440,000
Population 2030	77,800,000
Urban ratio	38%
Urban - Number of people per household	4.6
Rural - Number of people per household	5.5
Min grid interconnection	Yes
Electricity Demand Tiers	Tier 1: Small rural settlements =39.6 kWh/household/year Tier 2: Large rural settlements =300 kWh/household/year Tier 3: Urban areas =1440 kWh/household/year
Technology Assumptions	Grid connection limit: 50 km Mini-grid and SHS capital costs based on GET.transform and national benchmarks
Discount Rate	10–12%
Grid Losses	15% for LV and MV networks

2.3 Scenarios Modelled

- i. Scenario 1 (PSMP 2024) assumes 75% electricity access by 2030, with moderate electricity and demand growth, and limited new policy changes.
- ii. Scenario 2 (Energy Compact 2025) targets 100% access by 2030, with 1.5M new household connections per year, 75% renewables in the mix, and 20–30% off-grid access via SHS and mini-grids.

3. Results and Analysis

After running the two scenarios through on the OnSSET using a Jupyter notebook, the following are the results and analysis.

3.1 Scenario 1: Power System Master Plan 2024

The results of reaching the electrification of 75% of the population with different technologies are as shown in the table below.

Electrified by:	Population	Population %
Grid densification	38,684,898	50
Grid extension	4,243,533	5
SHS	9,863,366	13
Mini grids	5,556,803	7
Total	58,348,600	75

19,450,127(25%) of the population will be unelectrified in 2030.

The other results from scenario 1 are as shown in the figure below.

Electrification option	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)
Grid densification	1,681,717	647.48
Grid extension	909,477	109.35
SHS	2,138,171	104.06
Mini grids	1,027,883	419.5
Total	5,757,248	1,280.39

New Connections Vs. Electrification Optins

Capacity (MW) vs Electrification Options

The Investment required to reach 75% electrification.

Electrification option	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Investment %
Grid densification	1,387.1	26.2
Grid extension	1,155.6	21.9
SHS	1,611.6	30.5
Mini grids	1,131.9	21.4
Total	5,286.2	100

Investment (Million USD) Vs Electrification options

■ Grid densification ■ Grid extension ■ SHS ■ Mini grids

Tanzania Electrification rate of 75% in 2030

This scenario represents Tanzania’s business-as-usual electrification pathway under PSMP 2024, targeting 75% access by 2030. About 58.3 million people are expected to gain electricity, primarily through grid densification (50%), with smaller shares from grid extension (5%), Solar Home Systems (13%), and mini-grids (7%). Despite this progress, 25% of the population remains unelectrified, highlighting the need for greater investment in off-grid solutions to reach universal access.

3.2 Scenario 2: Tanzania Energy Compact 2025

This scenario explores an accelerated electrification pathway aligned with the Tanzania National Energy Compact 2025. It reflects the government’s commitment to achieving universal (100%) electricity access by 2030, with a significant scale-up of both grid and off-grid technologies. The model integrates policy ambitions, increased investment flows, and private sector participation to close the access gap beyond the PSMP 2024 baseline.

Electrified by:	Population	Population %
Grid densification	38,684,898	49.7
Grid extension	9,751,649	12.5
SHS	22,923,824	29.5
Mini grids	6,439,627	8.3
Total	77,799,998	100

Electrification option	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)
Grid densification	1,681,717	647.55
Grid extension	2,105,966	242.2
SHS	4,977,604	224.38
Mini grids	1,220,708	450.53
Total	9,985,995	1,564.66

Capacity (MW) Vs. Electrification Options

Electrification option	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Investment %
Grid densification	1,387.22	15.5
Grid extension	2,781.38	31.1
SHS	3,470.48	38.8
Mini grids	1,298.42	14.5
Total	8,937.5	

Investment (Millions USD) Vs. Electrification Options

This scenario achieves universal electricity access by 2030, connecting over 77 million people. Grid densification serves 49.7% of the population, grid extension 12.5%, Solar Home Systems 29.5%, and mini-grids 8.3%. It reflects a stronger push for decentralized solutions and inclusive rural electrification, supported by institutional reforms and an investment of \$8.94 billion under the Energy Compact.

4. Discussion

4.1 Insights and results implications

The modeling results present a clear contrast between Tanzania's two electrification scenarios. Under the PSMP 2024 (business-as-usual) pathway, the country is projected to reach 75% electricity access by 2030, with grid densification (50%) being the dominant technology. However, this still leaves approximately 25% of the population mostly in dispersed rural areas without access due to the economic and logistical limitations of grid extension.

In contrast, the Tanzania Energy Compact 2025 scenario demonstrates that universal access (100%) is achievable by 2030 through a balanced technology mix. Grid densification still plays a leading role (49.7%), but off-grid solutions, SHS (29.5%), and mini-grids (8.3%) account for nearly 38% of access. These findings highlight the necessity of decentralized electrification technologies and the importance of integrated planning that includes grid and off-grid approaches.

4.2 Potential Technologies and Policy Recommendations

The analysis emphasizes the following policy priorities and technology areas to achieve and sustain universal access:

i. Accelerate Deployment of Mini-Grids and SHS

Off-grid solutions are essential for remote and low-density settlements. The government should expand support mechanisms such as Results-Based Financing (RBF), reduce licensing barriers, and offer fiscal incentives for developers.

ii. Strengthening Grid Infrastructure

The Ministry of Energy, through TANESCO and REA, should invest in medium- and low-voltage infrastructure, smart grid technologies, and network reliability upgrades, which will be crucial as demand rises and urbanization expands.

iii. Institutionalizing Digital Planning Tools

Platforms such as OnSSET and QGIS should be formally integrated into national planning frameworks to improve targeting, reduce overlap, and align investments with actual needs.

iv. Enable Inclusive Financing

The Ministry of Finance and Energy should strengthen affordability through targeted subsidies, inclusive tariffs, and promotion of financing instruments such as green bonds and microloans for rural consumers.

4.3 Limitations of the study

- i. **Data Constraints:** While efforts were made to harmonize multiple datasets, gaps remain in the availability and accuracy of updated infrastructure data, especially for MV lines data, Health and Schools facilities, and informal settlements.
- ii. **Static Demand Modeling:** Demand tiers are fixed by settlement type and do not dynamically adjust for urbanization, economic growth, or shifts in consumption behavior over time.
- iii. **Financial Uncertainties:** Cost assumptions for technologies are based on current benchmarks and may not fully capture future price or exchange rate risks.
- iv. **Assumed Implementation Efficiency:** The scenarios assume ideal rollout conditions without accounting for delays in financing, procurement, land acquisition, or institutional bottlenecks.

4.4 Potential areas for future research

- i. **Affordability and Willingness-to-Pay Studies.** A better understanding of rural and peri-urban households' financial constraints can inform tariff and subsidy design for SHS and mini-grid solutions.
- ii. **Cross-border Electrification Opportunities.** Studying the potential for regional power trade and interconnectors to support electrification in border areas.
- iii. **Climate Resilience and Risk-Based Planning:** Integrating flood zones, drought-prone regions, and climate vulnerability into electrification models.
- iv. **E-mobility and Grid Impact:** Modeling the implications of electric vehicle adoption on load growth, especially in urban centers like Dar Es Salaam and Dodoma.
- v. **Decentralized Energy Governance:** Exploring the role of local governments and communities in planning, operating, and managing mini-grid and SHS networks.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Lessons learnt (Take Away)

This study demonstrates that achieving universal electricity access in Tanzania by 2030 is technically and economically feasible when both grid and off-grid strategies are deployed in a coordinated manner. The PSMP 2024 scenario, while progressing toward 75% access, falls short of covering the final mile. However, the Energy Compact 2025 scenario shows how an accelerated, integrated approach backed by investment, institutional reform, and policy support can close the access gap.

Key lessons include the need for: A multi-technology electrification strategy, a greater focus on rural and difficult-to-access communities, institutionalizing data-driven planning tools, and strengthening coordination across stakeholders.

5.2 Recommendations

- i. The Ministry of Energy and its agency and Local Government office should develop a national electrification dashboard to monitor access, investment flows, and implementation progress in real-time, enabling adaptive policy responses.
- ii. The Ministry of Energy, together with ICTP, to adapt the Integrated Planning Frameworks. The use of tools like OnSSET, QGIS, and updated census/geospatial data for least-cost, spatial planning must be optimized at the national and regional levels.
- iii. The Ministry of Finance, Energy, and development partners should mobilize investment for off-grid expansion. The Ministry of Energy should increase funding support for SHS and mini-grids through public-private partnerships (PPP), development finance, and climate financing instruments.
- iv. The Ministry of Energy should update Policy and Regulatory Instruments. EWURA should streamline licensing for mini-grids, update technical standards, and promote interoperability between grid and off-grid systems.
- v. Build Institutional and Human Capacity: The MoE/TANESCO, Vocational and Training Institutions (VETA), and Development Partners (e.g, SEforALL) should invest in training for national and local planners, engineers, and technicians to improve planning and execution capacity.

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